

100 cm or more (3%). Rice cultivar CR314-5-10, developed at CRURRS, was identified as the most promising culture for the bunded uplands.

CR314-5-10 derived from IR42/IR5853-118-5, is a semidwarf culture with stiff straw and takes about 115 d to mature. It has good early vigor, allowing proper stand establishment and competition with weeds. It possesses a fair degree of tolerance for drought in the vegetative phase and has long panicles (27.5 cm). Grains are long and slender (length:width = 3.2) with white kernels; 1,000-grain weight is 24.0 g.

CR314-5-10 was evaluated under direct seeded conditions in station trials and under transplanted conditions in all India Coordinated trials from 1983 to 1985. In station trials it produced significantly higher average yields than check variety Ratna over a 2-yr period

Table 2. Performance of CR314-5-10 in multilocal trials under transplanted conditions, Bihar, India, 1983-85.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering	Panicles (m ²)	Average yield ^a (t/ha)			
			Wet season		Dry season	
			1983 (20)	1984 (22)	1984 (6)	1985 (6)
CR314-5-10	94	288	3.9	3.4	4.3	4.2
Rasi	83	304	2.8	2.9	4.1	3.5
IR36	94	320	3.6	3.2	4.4	4.0
Increase (96)						
Over Rasi ^b					19	
Over IR36 ^b					4	

^aFigures in parentheses indicate the number of sites. ^bBased on mean of 4 seasons.

at Hazaribag and Kanke (Table 1). In the coordinated trials CR314-5-10 showed yield superiority to IR36 and Rasi (Table 2).

CR314-5-10 performed well under the lab-to-land program and was acceptable

to farmers. On the basis of its superiority in grain yield to the check varieties, coupled with its tolerance for drought and blast disease, it has the potential to replace Ratna and Rasi in the Chhotanagpur plateau. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Effect of hydrocortisone on germination of rice

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Hydrocortisone, a steroid hormone of higher animals, promotes cellular activity by influencing carbohydrate and protein metabolism. We studied its effect on germination and growth of rice seedlings.

Seeds of IR50 were soaked in 0, 50, 100, 200, and 500 ppm concentrations of hydrocortisone solution for 6 or 24 h. Germination increased up to 100 ppm with 6 h soaking (see table). Soaking for 24 h improved germination more than 6 h soaking. Root and shoot lengths nearly doubled with 100 ppm hydrocortisone. Hydrocortisone may have promoted cell elongation or multiplication of cells, or both.

Dry matter accumulation decreased with hydrocortisone, probably because

Effect of hydrocortisone on germination and seedling growth. Coimbatore, India.

Hydrocortisone concentration (ppm)	Germination (%)		Root length (cm)		Shoot length (cm)		Seedling dry weight (mg)	
	6 h	24 h	6 h	24 h	6 h	24 h	6 h	24 h
	0 (control)	60	80	7.13	7.06	3.79	3.07	16.08
50	70	85	7.87	8.28	4.22	3.29	15.25	14.94
100	80	85	14.29	13.76	8.07	7.33	14.90	15.00
200	60	85	6.42	7.89	3.39	3.08	15.25	15.70
500	65	70	6.21	5.85	3.55	2.34	15.23	17.00
CD	11	9	1.46	1.17	1.03	0.76	ns	1.54

of increased utilization of seed reserves. Higher maintenance respiration might also have contributed to lower dry matter accumulation.

Soaking in hydrocortisone for 24 h enhanced root growth but had a more adverse effect on shoot growth than soaking for 6 h. The 500 ppm concentration generally depressed germination and growth, perhaps because of the toxic effect of the chemical.

These findings suggest that hydrocortisone has the potential to increase cellular activities in plants.

Detailed studies on the effect of foliar hydrocortisone sprays at different growth stages on productivity are in progress. □

Genotype × planting system interaction for flowering in rice

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The number of days to flowering or

Genotype × system of planting interaction for flowering. Uttar Pradesh, India.

Direction of change in transplanting compared with direct seeding ^a (d)	Genotypes
0 (no change)	<i>Group 1</i> B2997-CTB-60-3-3, Rath, Sakun, Kn 361-1-B-6 IR6828-2-4, B635-2, NDR95, NDR311, Narendra 1
+ 1	<i>Group 2</i> NDR102, Jhona 349, Dular
+ 2	Dhaneshwar, Lalnakanda
+ 3	NDR80, DJ29, Tulzapur-1, Tetep
+ 4	Karahani, IAC25, D3-29
+ 5	Kinandang Patong, NDR118, Halamaldia, Ranikajal-A, Brown Cora
+ 6	Mala J15, Sarya-A, Lalmati
+ 7	Kalkeri, Dudhi A, Lalmati
+ 8	Kachni, N22. NDR88, NDR119
+ 9	Black Bagari, Kudia, Mutmuriya, NDR97
+10	Bagari White
+11	Culture 62
+12	Jalsar, Kolhapur Scented, NDR85
+13	NDR308
+14	IRAT115
+15	Dehula A, NDR115
+16	Bagari, Sawani, Ketki
+17	NDR132
-1	<i>Group 3</i> Mutmuri A, Mircirak, IR15784-14, IR4895- 1-2-1-8
-2	Annapurna, IRAT107
-3	ASD7, ARC10372, IET7041, NDR83
-4	Kiran, IET6973, IET7564
-5	CR245-1, NDR87
-6	Kanchan, Govind
-7	MW10, IET6639

^a+ = increase (delay), - decrease (earliness).

maturity is an important economic trait, and differences of even a few days can influence productivity, adaptability, cropping intensity, and cropping sequence. Compared with direct seeding, transplanting appears to extend the time to 50% flowering or by about 1 wk. However, observation of flowering among certain varieties under the two planting systems revealed differential behavior for that trait. One hundred genotypes with both dwarf and tall backgrounds from national and exotic sources were therefore grown simultaneously under the two systems.

Three groups were apparent (see table). The first group showed stable flowering behavior under both planting systems, the second exhibited a 1- to 17-d delay in flowering with transplanting, and the third showed 1-7 d earliness with transplanting.

The differential flowering responses of rice genotypes to direct seeding and transplanting might stem from their genetic variability with respect to plasticity for nutritional and hormonal imbalances within the plants. Seedlings uprooted for transplanting are subjected to physical mutilation that suddenly arrests the supply of water, nutrients, and other metabolites. There is also a time lag between uprooting of seedlings,

their transplanting, and further establishment in the soil. During this period the seedlings are subjected first to drought stress, then to flooding in the puddled field.

These sequential conditions are known to reduce cytokinin and gibberellin synthesis in the roots and also their transport to shoots. The mutilation effects may vary in magnitude in different genotypes, depending upon the growth behavior of the root system in the nursery and the delicateness of the seedlings.

Reduction in days to flowering in several rice genotypes on transplanting is still a baffling situation. □

Variability in bud number, bud length, and ratoon tillering in four rice varieties

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We studied ratoon tillering ability in three photoperiod-sensitive varieties — NC365, FR13A, and Patnai 23 — and a longduration, high yielding variety — IET5656 — sown on 15 Nov 1985 in Chinsurah.

The main crop was harvested May 1986. N fertilizer (10 kg/ ha) and irrigation water were applied to plots of all varieties 4 d after harvest. Viable buds per main tiller, bud length on the main tiller, and ratoon tillers per plant were measured for three cutting heights (see table).

Cutting height caused a significant difference in number of viable buds on the main tiller; however, the interaction effect of variety and cutting height was not significant. Viable buds were less with the ground level cut than with higher level cuts. The correlation between viable buds per main tiller and ratoon tillers per plant over all cutting heights was statistically nonsignificant but showed a moderately positive relationship in FR13A, Patnai 23, and IET5656.

Bud number, bud length, and ratoon tillering in 4 rice varieties at 3 cutting heights. Chinsurah, West Bengal, India, 1985-86.

Cutting height (cm)	Viable buds (no./ main tiller)	Bud length on main tiller (mm)	Ratoon tillers (no./plant)
<i>NC365</i>			
5	1.9	5.2	8.5
15	2.3	5.7	7.4
30	3.2	4.9	6.6
<i>FR13A</i>			
5	1.9	5.5	8.9
15	2.9	6.3	8.5
30	3.3	5.7	10.4
<i>Patnai 23</i>			
5	2.7	16.1	9.7
15	3.1	31.9	9.5
30	4.1	68.0	10.5
<i>IET5656</i>			
5	2.4	4.7	2.3
15	3.5	5.7	1.7
30	4.2	8.2	7.1
<i>F-value^a</i>			
Variety	25.05**	5.63*	3.27
Cutting height	54.11**	4.7*	5.7**
Variety × cutting height	0.96	3.87*	4.14*
CD (0.05)			
Variety	0.3	23.9	-
Variety × cutting height	0.3	10.1	0.4

^aSignificant at 1% (**) and 5% (*) levels.

The average bud length on the main tiller for different cutting heights did not differ among the varieties except in